

Prevalence of incidental findings in CT scan of paranasal sinuses

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ABSTRACT

Background: The use of computed tomography (CT) scans has become a common diagnostic tool for evaluating the paranasal sinuses (PNS), particularly in patients presenting with symptoms such as chronic sinusitis, nasal obstruction, or facial pain. CT imaging offers detailed visualization of sinus anatomy and pathology, often leading to accurate diagnosis and management. Incidental findings (IFs) are unintentional discoveries unrelated to the imaging purpose. Imaging exams on people with suspected intracranial diseases may detect IFs in the PNS. **Objectives:** The aim of the study was to evaluate the prevalence of incidental abnormalities on computed tomographic scans of the paranasal sinuses. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Radiology & Imaging, Uttara Adhunik Medical College & Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh during January 2023 to December 2023. A total of 120 patients were participated in the study. Statistical analyses of the results were obtained by using window-based Microsoft Excel and Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS-24). **Results:** The age distribution showed that (14.16%) patients were under 20 years old, (20.0%) were between 21 and 40 years old and 48 (40.0%) were over the age of 61. The majority of the patients were male (58.33%) and (41.66%) being female. According to employment status, (15.83%) of patients were housewives, (10%) were businessmen, (7.5%) were retired officers and (34.16%) were service members. According to socioeconomic level, (58.33%) of the patients come from middle-class families, (24.16%) from low-income families and (17.60%) from middle-class families. **Conclusion:** Incidental abnormalities on paranasal sinus CT scans are common, though most findings are minor and unlikely to require intervention. Awareness of these incidental findings is essential to avoid unnecessary follow-up and treatment, particularly when abnormalities do not correlate with symptoms. Further research is warranted to evaluate the clinical significance of specific types of incidental findings.

Keywords: Computed tomography (CT), Paranasal sinuses (PNS), Incidental findings (IFs).

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INTRODUCTION

Most physicians continue to struggle with diagnosing chronic inflammatory illness of the paranasal sinuses. Chronic sinusitis is defined as the presence of permanent tissue alterations in the lining membranes of one or more paranasal sinuses^[1]. This is a definition of the pathogenic state; however, diagnosis requires clinical and temporal correlates, which presents a challenge. The symptoms of chronic sinus disease are numerous and frequently vague and nonspecific, and physical examination is limited because the sinuses cannot be examined directly. As a result, radiographic examinations have an important diagnostic function. It is thus critical to determine the pathologic correlations of aberrant

radiographic appearances of the paranasal sinuses in patients with suspected chronic sinus illness.

Imaging incidental findings (IFs) are results that are not connected to the clinical indication. Computed tomography (CT) has greatly increased the ability to visualize organs and tissues, boosting the possibility of identifying novel discoveries due to its larger field of view. Furthermore, CT imaging is crucial for detecting and diagnosing cancers and atypical illnesses^[2]. Scientists have focused their efforts on determining the incidence rate and causes of IFs in brain CT imaging^[3]. As brain CT and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) become more widely available, medical experts are making an increasing number of surprising discoveries. Despite their

rising frequency, IFs in CT research differ depending on the population being studied^[4].

The description of an incidental discovery (IF) may need more medical care, potentially leading in unnecessary testing, diagnostic procedures, and therapies, which may offer an increased danger to the patient in certain situations. [5] Scholars including Hara, O'Sullivan et al., and Siddiki et al. have referred to this phenomenon as the cascading effect. The paranasal sinuses (PNS) feature a wide range of disorders known as IFs. These might range from minor issues like mucosal thickening or sinusitis to more serious ones like tumors or foreign objects. Several research studies have thoroughly described how the finding of an IF may result in the early and beneficial detection of an unanticipated tumor or aneurysm^[6]. Nonetheless, clinical expertise indicates that many IFs have unknown clinical importance, causing concern for both research participants and their healthcare professionals^[7].

The prevalence of incidental abnormalities on computed tomographic (CT) scans of the paranasal sinuses investigates how frequently unexpected findings appear in these scans, which are often conducted for reasons unrelated to sinus health. The findings reveal those incidental abnormalities—such as mucosal thickening, sinus opacification, and polyps—are quite common, even in asymptomatic individuals. These

abnormalities often have no clinical significance but can lead to unnecessary treatments if misinterpreted as requiring intervention. The study emphasizes the importance of carefully assessing incidental findings and distinguishing between clinically relevant and irrelevant abnormalities to avoid overtreatment and unnecessary procedures.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Radiology & Imaging, Uttara Adhunik Medical College & Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh January 2023 to December 2023. A total of 120 patients were participated in the study. Patients who have undergone CT scans of the paranasal sinuses for various indications within a specific timeframe were include inclusion criteria and patients with known sinus pathology, history of sinus surgery, or who are symptomatic for sinus disease were include exclusion criteria. After taking consent and matching eligibility criteria, data were collected from patients on variables of interest using the predesigned structured questionnaire by interview, observation. Statistical analyses of the results were be obtained by using window-based Microsoft Excel and Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS-24).

RESULTS

Table - I: Distribution of the study according to baseline characteristic (n=120)

	n=120	%
Age (years)		
≤20	17	14.16
21-40	24	20.00
41-60	31	25.83
≥61	48	40.00
Sex Distribution		
Male	70	58.33
Female	50	41.66
Occupational status		
House wife	19	15.83
Retried	09	7.5
Service	41	34.16
Day labour	24	20
Teacher	08	6.66
Farmer	07	5.83
Business	12	10
Socio-economic condition		
Low	29	24.16
Middle	70	58.33
High	21	17.60
BMI distribution		
<18.5 (Underweight)	18	15
18.5-24.9 (Normal)	34	28.33
25-29.9 (Overweight)	48	40
>30 (Obese)	20	16.66

Table I shows age distribution of the study population, it was observed that 17(14.16%) patients were belonged to age ≤20 years, 24(20.0%) patients were belonged to age 21-40 years,

31(25.83%) patients were belonged to age 41-60 years and 48(40.0%) patients were belonged to age ≥61 years. Table shows sex distribution of the study population; it was

observed that majority 70(58.33%) patients were male and 50(41.66%) patients were female. Table shows occupational status of the study population; it was observed that 19(15.83%) patients were house wives and 12(10%) patients were businessman. Followed by 9(7.5%) were retired officers and 41(34.16%) service holder and 24(20%) were day labour. Table shows socio-economic status of the study population, it

was observed that 70(58.33%) of the patients come from middle class family, 29(24.16%) of the patients come from low class and 21(17.60%) of the patients come from middle class family. The distribution of the study population according to BMI. It was observed that 48(40%) participants belonged to BMI 25-29.9 kg/m² (Overweight) and 34(28.33%) participants belonged to BMI 18.5-24.9 kg/m² (Normal).

Table - II: Prevalence of IFs according to patient gender

IFs	Gender	
	Male	Female
Acute sinusitis	9	8
Chronic sinusitis	4	1
Fungal infection	2	0
Mucocele	2	0
Polyp	3	2
Retention cyst	1	2
Total	21 (17.5)	13 (10.83)

Table II shows Prevalence of IFs according to patient gender, it was observed that according to 9% participants belonged to male group and 8% were female group. And according to

Chronic sinusitis, 4% participants belonged to male group and 1% were female group.

Table - III: The occurrence rate of IFs associated with the PNS

PNS	IFs	n=120	%
Ethmoid	Acute sinusitis	2	1.6
Ethmoid and Maxillary	Acute sinusitis	3	2.5
Frontal and Maxillary	Acute sinusitis	2	1.6
Maxillary	Acute sinusitis	13	10.83
	Chronic sinusitis	4	3.33
	Fungal infection	2	1.6
	Mucocele	2	1.6
	Polyp	5	4.16
	Retention cyst	3	2.5

Table III shows the occurrence rate of IFs associated with the PNS, it was observed that acute sinusitis was 13(10.83%),

Chronic sinusitis was 4(3.33%), Fungal infection was 2(1.6%) when PNS was Maxillary.

Table - IV: The incidence rate of IFs associated with each side

IFs side	IFs	n=120	%
Bilateral	Acute sinusitis	5	4.16
	Chronic sinusitis	3	2.5
	Polyp	2	1.6
Left	Acute sinusitis	7	5.83
	Chronic sinusitis	3	2.5
	Fungal infection	2	1.6
	Mucocele	2	1.6
	Polyp	2	1.6
	Retention cyst	2	1.6
Right	Acute sinusitis	6	5
	Polyp	3	2.5
	Retention cyst	2	1.6

Table IV shows the incidence rate of IFs associated with each side, it was observed that according to Bilateral, 5(4.16%),

3(2.5%) and 2(1.6%) were acute sinusitis, chronic sinusitis and polyp respectively.

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University, Dhaka. During one year of study period, total 120 samples were included in this study. The prevalence of incidental abnormalities on computed tomography (CT) scans of the paranasal sinuses has garnered significant attention due to the widespread use of imaging in medical diagnostics. CT scans of the paranasal sinuses are often performed to evaluate conditions such as chronic sinusitis, nasal obstruction, and facial pain. However, these scans frequently reveal unexpected, asymptomatic findings unrelated to the patient's presenting symptoms. These incidental abnormalities can include mucosal thickening, polyps, cysts, and other structural variations that may not necessarily indicate disease but can lead to further investigation or intervention.

Intracranial diseases, which include tumors, infections, and traumatic injuries, are typically examined utilizing imaging modalities such as CT and MRI. These imaging techniques not only provide critical diagnostic information regarding anomalies in the skull, but they also detect unexpected findings in surrounding structures, such as the PNS^[8]. The incidence of IFs in the PNS during imaging exams for intracranial diseases has not been well recorded, and the clinical importance of these findings is currently debated. It is critical to understand the frequency of IFs in PNS while evaluating intracranial diseases. This understanding is critical for proper treatment and monitoring of certain IFs^[9,10].

In this present study, the age distribution showed that 17 (14.16%) patients were under 20 years old, 24 (20.0%) were between 21 and 40 years old, 31 (25.83%) were between 41 and 60 years old, and 48 (40.0%) were over the age of 61. In this study, the majority of the patients were male (58.33%), with 50 (41.66%) being female.

The study discovered that males are more vulnerable than females, which is consistent with prior research showing a higher prevalence of PNS abnormalities in males^[11]. Males typically encounter sinusitis-causing variables at work, such as dusty and polluted workplaces. This is similar with the findings of Ertugay et al. and Gupta et al., who discovered a higher proportion of females in their study, which deviates from the prevailing male dominance^[12,13]. Most importantly, the study found that older persons were more likely to have PNS anomalies, which is consistent with earlier research^[9]. This could be because the PNS changes as people age, such as a reduction in the ability to clear mucus by cilia movement and a fall in immunological function. These modifications make the peripheral nervous system more susceptible to infection and other disorders^[14].

Our study presents that, the prevalence of IFs by patient gender was found to be 9% male and 8% female. According to Chronic sinusitis, 4% of participants were male, whereas 1% were female. In terms of the occurrence rate of IFs linked with the PNS, acute sinusitis was 13 (10.83%), chronic sinusitis was 4 (3.33%), and fungal infection was 2 (1.6%).

A study found that conservative measures, such as monitoring and follow-up imaging, can effectively manage these IFs, even if they are of limited clinical value. When evaluating neurological disorders, a brain MRI frequently detects abnormal PNS. In general, these IFs are benign, with the most prevalent symptom being increased mucosal lining thickness^[15]. Males and people aged 35 and younger accounted for the majority of chance findings. Detecting anomalous observations in the PNS aids in the diagnosis of anomalies unrelated to the suspected neurological illness^[15]. A detailed evaluation was also performed on 192 sinus CT scans of individuals with a documented history of rhinosinusitis.

A study was done to look into the development of IFS in the PNS of people who did not exhibit symptoms. The study discovered that 56% of patients had opacity, with thickening of the mucosal lining being the most common reason. Scores of 15 or higher indicated the possibility of severe opacification. Participants in this group were more likely to develop symptoms throughout the follow-up period than those with no or just minor results. As a result, a significant inadvertent sinus opacity on CT scans suggests the possibility of having a respiratory problem in the future^[16].

This study observed that, the incidence rate of IFs related with each side was observed to be 5(4.16%), 3(2.5%), and 2(1.6%) for acute sinusitis, chronic sinusitis, and polyps, respectively. The rates of acute sinusitis, chronic sinusitis, fungal infection, and retention cyst on the left side were 2 (1.6%), 7 (5.83%), 2 (1.6%), and 2 (1.6%), respectively. The rates of right IFS side acute sinusitis, polyps, and retention cysts were 6 (5%), 3 (2.5%), and 2 (1.6%), respectively.

The most common normal variations observed were nasal septal deviation, Agger nasi cells, and sphenoid sinuses that extended into the posterior nasal septum. There was no significant difference in the frequency of any of the anatomical abnormalities investigated between patients with minor and medically important disorders affecting the PNS or nasal cavity. As a result, routine CT scans of the PNS, which are used to identify sinusitis or rhinitis by detecting anatomical changes, are worthless unless surgery is scheduled^[17]. The findings are consistent with another study that revealed a higher prevalence of anomalies in the maxillary sinus compared to the other sinuses^[18]. However, the impacts on the ethmoid and frontal sinuses were less common. The study also discovered that abnormalities were more common on the left than on the right, with both sides having abnormalities in 25.9% of cases^[18].

Understanding the prevalence of these incidental findings is essential for clinicians in differentiating between clinically relevant abnormalities and benign variations. It also aids in guiding patient management, avoiding unnecessary treatments, and reducing patient anxiety over incidental findings. Studies on the prevalence of these findings suggest that incidental abnormalities on sinus CT scans are common, even among asymptomatic individuals, highlighting the importance of cautious interpretation and patient-centered decision-making in clinical practice.

Limitations of the study

The present study was conducted in a very short period due to time constraints and funding limitations. The small sample size was also a limitation of the present study.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of incidental abnormalities on computed tomographic (CT) scans of the paranasal sinuses generally highlights that incidental sinus abnormalities are common, even in asymptomatic individuals. Findings often include mucosal thickening, sinus opacification, and other anatomical variations, which are detected at rates ranging from 30-50% in some studies. Most of these incidental findings do not correlate with clinical symptoms or require treatment. While incidental sinus abnormalities on CT scans are frequently observed, they are typically clinically insignificant. Therefore, caution is advised to avoid overdiagnosis and overtreatment, focusing instead on correlating radiologic findings with clinical symptoms before deciding on interventions.

RECOMMENDATION

This study can serve as a pilot to much larger research involving multiple centers that can provide a nationwide picture, validate regression models proposed in this study for future use and emphasize points to ensure better management and adherence.

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REFERENCE

1. Havas TE, Motbey JA, Gullane PJ. Prevalence of incidental abnormalities on computed tomographic scans of the paranasal sinuses. *Archives of Otolaryngology-Head & Neck Surgery*. 1988 Aug 1;114(8):856-9.
2. O'Sullivan JW, Muntinga T, Grigg S, Ioannidis JP. Prevalence and outcomes of incidental imaging findings: umbrella review. *bmj*. 2018 Jun 18;361.
3. Hara AK. Extracolonial findings at CT colonography. In *Seminars in Ultrasound, CT and MRI 2005 Feb 1 (Vol. 26, No. 1, pp. 24-27)*. WB Saunders.
4. Siddiki H, Fletcher JG, McFarland B, Dajani N, Orme N, Koenig B, Strobel M, Wolf SM. Incidental findings in CT colonography:

literature review and survey of current research practice. *Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics*. 2008 Jul;36(2):320-31.

5. Hamdi AA. Role of Computed Tomography in Determining the Spectrum of Paranasal Sinuses Pathologies in Saudi patients (Master's thesis, Alfaisal University (Saudi Arabia)).
6. Gluecker TM, Johnson CD, Wilson LA, MacCarty RL, Welch TJ, Vanness DJ, Ahlquist DA. Extracolonial findings at CT colonography: evaluation of prevalence and cost in a screening population. *Gastroenterology*. 2003 Apr 1;124(4):911-6.
7. Casarella WJ. A patient's viewpoint on a current controversy. *Radiology*. 2002 Sep;224(3):927-.
8. Zidan MM, Abdalaziz I, Elnour AM, Alghamdi SS, Mahmoud MZ, Ali WM, Abd-Elgyoum AM. Prevalence and clinical importance of the incidental findings in brain MRI examinations. *Bioscience Research*. 2020;17(2):888-93.
9. Ali AH, Serhan OO, Alsharif MH, Elamin AY, Al-Ghamdi S, Aldossari KK, Alrudian N, Alajmi M, Alhariqi BA, Mokhatrish M, Palanivel V. Incidental detection of paranasal sinuses abnormalities on CT imaging of the head in Saudi adult population. *Plos one*. 2022 Sep 2;17(9): e0270764.
10. Hansen AG, Helvik AS, Nordgård S, Bugten V, Stovner LJ, Håberg AK, Gårseth M, Eggesbø HB. Incidental findings in MRI of the paranasal sinuses in adults: a population-based study (HUNT MRI). *BMC ear, nose and throat disorders*. 2014 Dec; 14:1-7.
11. Kushwah AP, Bhalse R, Pande S. CT evaluation of diseases of Paranasal sinuses & histopathological studies. *Int J Med Res Rev*. 2015;3(11):1306-0.
12. Ertugay ÇK, Koç AÖ, Çevik H, Erbek S. How much are the incidental abnormalities on brain MRI clinically significant in otolaryngology practice? *ENT Updates*. 2016 Feb 1;6(3).
13. Gupta MK, Rauniyar RK, Ahmad K, Ansari S, Pant AR. Incidental mucosal abnormalities of paranasal sinus in patients referred for MRI brain for suspected intracranial pathology in Eastern Nepal. *Asian Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2014 Feb 25;5(3):40-4.
14. Busaba NY. The impact of a patient's age on the clinical presentation of inflammatory paranasal sinus disease. *American Journal of Otolaryngology*. 2013 Sep 1;34(5):449-53.
15. Almushayti ZA. Assessment of Paranasal Sinus Pathology in Patients Presenting for Brain MRI as Referred from General Practice or Neurologist Physicians. *Cureus*. 2022 Oct;14(10).
16. Araújo-Neto SA, Baracat EC. Clinical progression of incidental tomographic findings in paranasal sinuses of asymptomatic individuals: cohort study. *Jornal de pediatria*. 2011; 87:433-8.
17. Shpilberg KA, Daniel SC, Doshi AH, Lawson W, Som PM. CT of anatomic variants of the paranasal sinuses and nasal cavity: poor correlation with radiologically significant rhinosinusitis but importance in surgical planning. *American Journal of Roentgenology*. 2015 Jun;204(6):1255-60.
18. Drummond JP, Allegro BB, Novo NF, de Miranda SL, Sendyk WR. Evaluation of the prevalence of maxillary sinuses abnormalities through spiral computed tomography (CT). *International archives of otorhinolaryngology*. 2017 Apr;21(02):126-33.